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ENSURING INVESTMENT AND INFRASTRUCTURE DEVELOPMENT OF THE UNITED TERRITORIAL COMMUNITIES OF THE REGION IN THE CONDITIONS OF DECENTRALIZATION OF POWER

ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ ІНВЕСТИЦІЙНОГО ТА ІНФРАСТРУКТУРНОГО РОЗВИТКУ ОБ'ЄДНАНИХ ТЕРИТОРІАЛЬНИХ ГРОМАД РЕГІОНУ В УМОВАХ ДЕЦЕНТРАЛІЗАЦІЇ ВЛАДИ

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Добрянська Н.А., Торішня Л.А., Буковський Д.А. Забезпечення інвестиційного та інфраструктурного розвитку об'єднаних територіальних громад регіону в умовах децентралізації влади. Оглядова стаття.

Стаття присвячена висвітленню реформи децентралізації в Україні та забезпеченню інвестиційного і інфраструктурного розвитку об'єднаних територіальних громад в умовах децентралізації влади. Проаналізовано законодавчу базу реформи децентралізації. Представлена умовна структура органів управління територіальних громад. Зазначено основні завдання керівників громад, а також запропоновані основні заходи, які допоможуть залучити інвестиції та створити якісну інфраструктуру в територіальних громадах. Охарактеризовано інструменти по залученню інвестицій до територіальних громад.

Ключові слова: децентралізація, органи місцевого самоврядування, територіальна громада, соціальна інфраструктура, інвестиційний розвиток

Dobrianska N.A., Torishnya L.A., Bukovskiy D.A. Ensuring investment and infrastructural development of the united territorial communities of the region in the conditions of decentralization of power. Review article.

The article is devoted to the coverage of decentralization reform in Ukraine and ensuring investment and infrastructural development of united territorial communities in the conditions of decentralization of power. The legislative base of decentralization reform is analyzed. The conditional structure of governing bodies of territorial communities is presented. The main tasks of community leaders are indicated, as well as the main measures proposed to help attract investment and create a quality infrastructure in local communities. Instruments for attracting investment to local communities are described.

Keywords: decentralization, local self-government bodies, territorial community, social infrastructure, investment development

Ukraine has reformed the decentralization of power to build an effective system of local self-government, because without an effective and efficient system of local self-government it is impossible to reach a new level in socio-economic and cultural development of territorial communities and regions, improve the level and quality of life. That is why the role of local self-government has changed in recent years: from a novice in economic relations, it has become an active participant in equal interaction with other partners in economic processes. Decentralization reform through the creation of territorial communities is designed to ensure the development of territories, create transport, educational, medical, housing and communal, physical culture and sports and cultural infrastructure.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Specialists in the field of public administration and local self-government, lawyers, politicians, civil servants, local self-government officials, as well as scientists paid considerable attention to the development of territorial communities. Issues of development of territorial communities are revealed in the works of T.M. Baranovska, K.O. Linyova, O.E. Obolensky, V.V. Mamonova, Y.A. Tihomirova, P.D. Bilenchuk.

The purpose of the article is to develop tools to ensure investment and infrastructural development of united territorial communities in the context of decentralization of power.

The main part

The direction and logic of local self-government reform were defined in the Concept of Reforming Local Self-Government and Territorial Organization of Power in Ukraine, approved by the Government on April 1, 2014. The concept includes the following main areas: administrative-territorial reform, fiscal decentralization, expansion of powers of local governments, reform of state regional policy. In addition, territorial communities have the right to dispose of land resources within their territory, to pool their property and resources through cooperation of territorial communities to implement joint programs and more efficient provision of public services to the population of adjacent territorial communities. The main tasks underlying decentralization include: the transfer of powers from the executive to the level of territorial communities and the allocation of sufficient financial resources; clear division of powers between executive bodies and between different levels of local self-government; strengthening the responsibility of bodies and officials of local self-government for their decisions to voters and the state [1].

In addition to the Concept of Reforming Local Self-Government and Territorial Authority in

Ukraine, the legislative framework for decentralization reform should include the Constitution of Ukraine [2], the European Charter of Local Self-Government [3], and the Law of Ukraine "On Voluntary Association of Territorial Communities" [4], The Law of Ukraine "On Local Self-Government" [5], the Law of Ukraine "On Cooperation of Territorial Communities" [6] and the Law of Ukraine "On Principles of State Regional Policy" [7].

After the decentralization reform, the main territorial unit became a territorial community - residents united by permanent residence within a village, town, city, which are independent administrative-territorial units, or a voluntary association of residents of several villages with a single administrative center [8]. That is, the community is the main (basic) link of local self-government. It has a chairman and an executive committee that performs all community management functions. The conditional structure of the governing bodies of the territorial community is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conditional structure of territorial community governing bodies

Source: authors' own development

Thus, local communities are called to plan their own development, set and implement strategic objectives of local importance, attract investment, develop the economy, promote local entrepreneurship, build quality roads, playgrounds, sports facilities and other places of recreation and leisure, as well as create jobs. However, all this is not easy to do, because to build a developed infrastructure is a very expensive process. Therefore, local authorities, in addition to being able to skillfully and effectively manage the local budget, must also attract investors to their communities.

Under conditions of decentralization, local councils have been given much more authority and responsibility at the same time. One of the priority areas of their activity is the development of territories and ensuring the well-being of residents. This requires developing the financial stability of the community, which is possible through increased tax revenues. The revenue part of the budget is formed mainly at the

expense of the local budget and working residents. The level of employment and budget occupancy depends on how the community contributes to the formation of new enterprises. Therefore, attracting investors should be one of the priorities of communities [9].

The process of attracting investors begins with an analysis of the business operating in the community and identifying key value chains. It is also equally important to determine the list of entities that the community can offer to investors – vacant land, premises, property complexes. The work of attracting investors must be systematic and the main task is to outline the benefits of your community using all possible channels of communication.

This includes participation in specialized exhibitions, forums, information in the media and media platforms, sending proposals to potentially interested companies, organizing and conducting presentations. However, in order to carry out work to

attract investment, you need to have the necessary tools – a community investment passport and

investment proposals for each of the proposed facilities (Figure 2) [10].

Figure 2. Tools for attracting investment to local communities

Source: authors' own development

The community investment passport is a tool for forming a positive image of the territorial community and increasing the investment activity of local business. The main tasks of the community investment passport:

- to form a positive image of an open community for doing business;
- inform about the investment opportunities of the local community;
- indicate the benefits of your local community;
- attract investors.

Community investment passport is a document consisting of several sections;

- 1 Section – appeal of the head of the territorial community to potential investors.
- 2 Section – describes the general characteristics of the territorial community (natural and climatic conditions; description of the social infrastructure of the community (education, culture, medicine, sports, leisure); labor resources; transport infrastructure; budget; economic structure; investment development).
- 3 Section – specific proposals for investors are indicated (leisure labor resources; transport infrastructure; budget; economic structure; investment development, project, etc.).

- 4 Section – contains contact information for investors (legal name and address of the community, its phone, fax and e-mail, website, QR code).

In order to attract investors. If you pay attention to the investment passport of the territorial community, all information must be written clearly and beautifully, using graphs, charts, tables, figures. Then investors will see the interest of local authorities, its serious approach to business. Another important point is the duplication of information in English. It is possible that in the future it will be possible to attract foreign partners to a certain community.

Thus, the attracted investment in the community will help create new jobs, which in turn will reduce the outflow of labor from the community to the regional center, as well as promote the development of infrastructure, industry and agriculture. Due to the creation of new jobs and the gradual growth of production, tax revenues to the local budget will increase, which will also have positive consequences, as the community will receive a larger income, which will direct funds to further social and economic well-being.

Figure 3. Benefits of attracting investment for the community

Source: authors' own development

Ensuring its infrastructural development is important for building a successful and prosperous community. Infrastructure is understood as a complex of so-called infrastructural branches of economy

(education, culture, transport, communication, sports, medicine). There are the following types of infrastructure: production and social (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Types of infrastructure
Source: authors' own development

All settlements in the community should be provided with paved entrances. Transport connections in rural areas by public roads should ensure the accessibility of villages to district and regional centers, centers of Starostyn districts. Road transport plays a leading role in both internal and external public relations. In addition, it serves and complements the railway. Transport routes of both regional and district significance should be developed on the territory of the community [10].

The development of social infrastructure is very important for the community, because a strong local community is a social local community. Therefore, the population must be fully provided with education, culture, medicine, physical culture and sports. After all, they say in vain, if you do not invest in education and sports today, tomorrow will have to finance prisons. That is why communities today must develop education and sports and continue to build a society of successful and happy people.

Community education policy is provided by secondary schools and preschools. The main challenges facing community education are the functioning of educational institutions in the context of education reform, as well as the unfavorable demographic situation, which may ultimately lead to the closure of some schools in rural areas, as it will be costly and impractical to maintain schools, in which 50 or less children study. Therefore, the transport infrastructure on the territory of communities should be developed, school buses will be purchased, which will take children to school to the neighboring settlement. The issue of children's nutrition in educational institutions is becoming important. Preschool children should be provided with quality three-course meals. As for schoolchildren, food should be provided to students from grades 1 to 11, and free meals should be provided to privileged categories of children (orphans, children deprived of parental care, children from low-income families, children of migrants, etc.). That is, the community leadership should be constantly in dialogue with the heads of educational institutions, parents on the organization of the educational process, nutrition, etc.

There should be a children's and youth art house and a children's and youth sports school on the territory of the community. The local children's and youth sports school is designed to educate young athletes, instill a love of sports and physical culture. That is why in no case can it be closed or reduced

funding for the maintenance of children's and youth sports school. Conversely, it is necessary to attract the best coaches, specialists to work in the children's and youth sports school, so that the result was as good as possible. In schools, it is necessary to instill in children a love of sports and physical culture, to pay considerable attention to this.

Physical culture and sports play an important role in shaping, strengthening, maintaining public health, improving efficiency and increasing the life expectancy [12]. By the Law of Ukraine "On Local Self-Government in Ukraine" of May 27, 1997 №280/97, the state enshrined the right of local self-government bodies to participate in the management of physical culture and health and sports activities [5].

Accordingly, residents of local communities should be able to engage in various sports: football, mini-football, basketball, handball, volleyball, athletics, chess, checkers, boxing, dancing and more. And for these sports you need the appropriate infrastructure and coaches or teachers. If there is such an infrastructure, it is necessary, firstly, to use the existing infrastructure skillfully and effectively, secondly, to treat all sports grounds carefully, and thirdly, to try to modernize and improve the existing sports facilities in the community.

Infrastructure is the basis for the development of physical culture and sports. If there is a well-developed sports infrastructure in the community, the probability that the community will be successful in sports increases several times. It is clear that the local budget cannot constantly finance the construction of sports facilities in the community, finance sports activities that promote sports among the population and maintain physical education facilities. All this is a big burden for the local budget, so the community must develop its investment attractiveness, as attracting investment is a new opportunity for community development.

No less important step, which is aimed at developing physical culture and sports, a healthy way life, leisure in the community, is the promotion of a healthy lifestyle among the population. How to do it? Hold regular sports competitions in the community, organize sports events such as "Movement is great!", "Dad, Mom, I'm a sports family", as well as constantly work with young people in the format of conversations, lectures on the importance of sports and physical culture. All activities must be covered on social networks and in the local media.

For the effective development of education and sports, an education, youth and sports department must be established. The department organizes the procedures of the educational process in educational institutions, creates programs for the comprehensive development of children; is engaged in development of youth policy, social protection of children, observance of realization of the rights by children; provides the relationship of parents-children-schools-local governments for the organic functioning of these categories in the context of the new educational space of the community. In addition, the community should adopt appropriate programs for the development of education and sports, which set out the main directions of development of these areas, the expected results, funding and responsible persons.

Health is a core value, important in the life of every person, is a key aspect of national security, determines the possibilities of achieving individual and social well-being and well-being, the prospects for sustainable development. Thus, health care or medicine is also an important area of community development, especially at a time when we are living in a COVID-19 pandemic. It is a dangerous acute respiratory disease that has claimed the lives of more than fifty thousand Ukrainians. That is why in our reality communities must be well provided for medically. There should be medical and obstetric points, outpatient clinics, an outpatient department and an ambulance station on their territories. In the community, health care facilities must provide outpatient care, provide medical care at home, provide home care for pregnant women and children under 1 year, to conduct health education among the population [13]. In communities and in Ukraine, in general, it is necessary to solve the problems of stabilizing the demographic situation, reducing morbidity, reducing mortality, stabilizing the situation of such dangerous diseases as COVID-19, hypertension, diabetes, HIV / AIDS, tuberculosis.

The work of cultural institutions should be aimed at meeting the informational, cultural, educational, aesthetic needs of the community. Usually, in rural areas, cultural institutions are local houses of culture, museums and libraries. The work of cultural institutions is aimed at preserving and developing the Ukrainian national culture, intensifying the activities of cultural institutions, ways to preserve the existing network and strengthen their role in the development of national – cultural revival, improving the material and technical base. Cultural institutions should hold holidays, festivals, competitions, and other cultural and artistic events related to the celebration of

calendar and memorable dates in Ukraine and in the community. For greater efficiency in the development of culture in the community, a department of culture, religions and tourism should be established in the executive committee. The department should be responsible for conducting meaningful, interesting leisure for the community, involving more children and youth in cultural and educational activities and organizational formations [14-18].

Thus, summarizing the development of social infrastructure in the community, the following measures should be identified that will help to develop it effectively:

- allocation of significant funds from the local budget for the development of social infrastructure;
- creation of profile structural subdivisions (departments, sectors) that were engaged and were responsible for the development of education, medicine, culture, physical culture and sports, tourism, leisure, etc.; physical culture and sports of the territorial community for 2022-2026 or the Program of development of education of the territorial community for 2022-2026);
- constant dialogue of local authorities with investors, patrons and volunteers who are ready to help and develop local social infrastructure.

All these measures will help local communities to build a developed social infrastructure, which in turn will positively affect their integrity, economic and social life, will revitalize everyday life and be able to reduce health care costs. But only if there is a consistent and systematic action plan.

Conclusions

Thus, ensuring the infrastructural and investment development of territorial communities in the context of decentralization of power is a very important and difficult issue, because communities now have to solve this issue independently, to approach it comprehensively. This is a new experience for local communities, they have been given the appropriate powers and responsibilities, at the same time, the development of infrastructure and investment on the ground depends on the local government chosen by the residents. That is why local authorities must do everything possible to ensure that the inhabitants of the respective territorial communities can exercise their right to modern medicine and education, accessible and high-quality administrative, communal, social services and developed infrastructure.

Abstract

Ukraine has reformed the decentralization of power to build an effective system of local self-government, because without an effective and efficient system of local self-government it is impossible to reach a new level in socio-economic and cultural development of territorial communities and regions, improve the level and quality of life. That is why the role of local self-government has changed in recent years: from a novice in economic relations, it has become an active participant in equal interaction with other partners in economic processes. The reform of decentralization through the creation of territorial communities is designed to ensure

the development of territories, to create transport, educational, medical, housing and communal, physical culture and sports and cultural infrastructure.

After the decentralization reform, the main territorial unit became a territorial community - residents united by permanent residence within a village, settlement, city, which are independent administrative-territorial units, or a voluntary association of residents of several villages with a single administrative center. That is, the community is the main (basic) link of local self-government. It has a chairman and an executive committee that performs all community management functions

Under decentralization, local councils have been given much more power and responsibility at the same time. One of the priority areas of their activity is the development of territories and ensuring the well-being of residents. This requires developing the financial stability of the community, which is possible through increased tax revenues. The revenue part of the budget is formed mainly at the expense of the local budget and working residents. The level of employment and budget occupancy depends on how the community contributes to the formation of new enterprises. Therefore, attracting investors should be one of the priorities of communities.

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Ensuring its infrastructural development is important for building a successful and prosperous community. Infrastructure is understood as a complex of so-called infrastructural branches of economy (education, culture, transport, communication, sports, medicine). There are the following types of infrastructure: production and social.

All settlements in the community should be provided with paved entrances. Transport connections in rural areas by public roads should ensure the accessibility of villages to district and regional centers, centers of Starostyn districts. Road transport plays a leading role in both the community's internal and external relations. In addition, it serves and complements the railway. Transport routes of both regional and district importance should be developed on the territory of the community.

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Thus, ensuring the infrastructural and investment development of territorial communities in the conditions of decentralization of power is a very relevant and difficult issue, because communities now have to solve this issue independently, to approach it comprehensively. This is a new experience for local communities they have been given the appropriate powers and responsibilities at the same time. At present, the development of infrastructure and investment on the ground depends on the local government elected by the residents. That is why local authorities must do everything possible to ensure that the inhabitants of the respective territorial communities can exercise their right to modern medicine and education, accessible and high-quality administrative, communal, social services and developed infrastructure.

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